

Quantum Mechanical Study of the Collinear Reaction $\text{He} + \text{H}_2^+ \rightarrow \text{HeH}^+ + \text{H}$

TOMI JOSEPH and N. SATHYAMURTHY*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur-208 016

We present here the results of an R-matrix investigation of the reaction $\text{He} + \text{H}_2^+ \rightarrow \text{HeH}^+ + \text{H}$ in collinear geometries for different vibrational states ($v=0-5$) of H_2^+ in the total energy range 0.95–1.44 eV. We identify the oscillations in the reaction probability as a function of energy as scattering resonances.

THE reaction,
 $\text{He} + \text{H}_2^+ \rightarrow \text{HeH}^+ + \text{H}$ (1)

has been the focus of attention of a variety of experimental and theoretical studies¹⁻³ for the last two decades for several reasons: (i) it is perhaps the first system for which experimental evidence of vibrational enhancement was established, (ii) it is a typical ion-molecule reaction and (iii) it is a three-electron system (isoelectronic with H_3) for which the potential energy surface (PES) could be computed to near chemical accuracy (± 1 kcal mol⁻¹). We have recently fitted an analytic function to the *ab initio* PES⁴ and carried out an extensive three dimensional (3D) quasiclassical trajectory (QCT) study of the reaction⁵. Our results are in excellent accord with the available experimental results^{1,3}. An exact quantum mechanical (QM) treatment of 3D reactive scattering is difficult and has been carried out only for the reaction

so far^{4,5}. Earlier QM calculations⁶ for the reaction (1) were, of necessity, restricted to collinear geometry and they also made use of a diatomic-in-molecules fit⁷ to the LCAO-MO-SCF results⁸ for the PES. They showed that the reaction probability (P^R) was a highly oscillatory function of the total energy E and attributed the oscillations to quantum mechanical resonances.

In this paper, we report the results of our collinear QM calculations for the reaction (1) on the accurate *ab initio* PES⁴ for different vibrational states ($v=0-5$) of H_2^+ over the energy range $E=0.955-1.44$ eV. We also attribute the oscillations in $P^R(E)$ to scattering resonances.

Methodology :

We have used the R-matrix approach of Light and Walker⁹ to solve the collinear coupled equations. Since the details of the method are given elsewhere⁹, we only state that the configuration space was partitioned into different regions as illustrated in Fig. 1. The various different parameters used in the computation are listed in Table 1. The details of the functional fit of the *ab initio* surface are given elsewhere⁴.

Fig. 1. The coordinate system used in the R-matrix calculation. For illustration, it is superimposed on the potential-energy contours for the system, in kcal. mol⁻¹ units relative to the reactants (He, H_2^+).

TABLE 1—PARAMETERS USED FOR QM CALCULATION

	Configuration	
	α ($\text{He} + \text{H}_2^+$)	γ ($\text{HeH}^+ + \text{H}$)
R^∞	12.0	10.5
R^{TC}	7.955	8.968
r^{TC}	4.398	3.310
r_{eq}	1.559	1.451
Scale factor (c)	0.788	0.990
No. of sectors	80	74
Basis N(P)	20(17)	20(17)

All distances are in scaled units (bohr). R^∞ is the asymptotic separation of an atom from a diatom, R^{TC} and r^{TC} are the coordinates of the turning center, r_{eq} is the equilibrium molecular separation, N is the number of primitive harmonic oscillator basis functions and P the number of dynamically contracted ones.

The R-matrix approach, unlike many of the initial value methods, is very stable to the inclusion of closed channels and permits relatively large stepsizes for slowly varying potentials. Also, the

transformation to the dynamical basis needs to be done only for the first collision energy of interest. This energy becomes an implicit parameter of the dynamical basis used at other energies. We have used $E=1.3$ eV to construct the dynamical basis. The values of P^R reported above this energy may not be truly converged ones.

Results and Discussion

The quantal P^R values for different v states of H_2^+ for the range $0.955 \leq E \leq 1.44$ eV are plotted in Figs. 2 and 3. Even at the threshold energy for the reaction of 0.955 eV (with respect to the bottom of the H_2^+ potential-energy curve), P^R is substantially above zero. In agreement with the earlier QM results⁶, we find $P^R(E)$ to be an oscillatory function. Interestingly the $P^R(E)$ for the reverse reaction,

remains nearly constant around unity. This is because, for $E < 1.32$ eV, only one channel ($v'=0$)

is open in the (HeH^+, H) region and as a result, P^R for the reaction (3) is obtained as a sum of P^R for the reaction (1) from all the open v states.

In contrast to the experimental result¹ and our 3D QCT result⁸ which show substantial vibrational enhancement for reaction (1), our QM results fail to show any appreciable vibrational enhancement of P^R . In fact, except between $v=0$ and 1, P^R decreases with increase in the vibrational excitation of H_2^+ to $v=2$ and above. This must be due to the special nature of the PES and the reduced dimensionality of the problem as was suggested earlier by Kuntz and Whitton¹⁰. Our collinear QCT calculations also fail to show any vibrational enhancement⁸. The fact that the QCT results, on the average, are in accord with the QM results is illustrated in Fig. 2, for $v=0$.

In order to attribute the oscillations in $P^R(E)$ to resonances in reactive scattering, we have plotted an Argand diagram for the S_{00}^R matrix element along with the variation of the corresponding phases with E in Fig. 4. From these plots, two overlapping

Fig. 2. Collinear QM reaction probability as a function of E for different vibrational states of H_2^+ .

Fig. 3. Same as Fig. 2, at a higher energy range. The arrow along the E axis represents "the" threshold energy for the $v'=1$ state of the product, HeH^+ .

Fig. 4. Argand diagram and the corresponding energy dependence of the phase for S_{00}^R . Numbers in the Argand diagram refer to the E values in eV.

resonances can be identified, one centered at $E=1.00$ eV and another at 1.01 eV. Many of the resonances can be identified from the P_{00}^R plots (Figs. 2 and 3); but many of them are overlapping with each other making their analysis extremely difficult.

The resonances detected in the collinear calculations may or may not be noticeable in the full 3D results. However, extensive studies of the 1D and 3D resonances for the reaction,

have shown that a collinear study can predict the location and width of some of the resonances in 3D satisfactorily¹¹. By accounting for the zero-point-bending energy of the transition state, the shift in the position of the resonance in going from 1D to 3D can be predicted reliably provided the reaction is dominated by a collinear approach. From an analysis of the PES, we have found⁸ that the reaction (1) does not have any such favoured approach. Hence, the results based on collinear calculations may not be representative of the 3D results. Unfortunately, a 3D QM calculation of resonances is still a formidable task. In this regard a recent approach by Shoemaker and Wyatt¹² based on Feshbach projection operator theory is somewhat promising. However, the theory has been developed at present only to symmetric reactions of the type $\text{A} + \text{BA}$, and is computationally very slow and expensive. Another approach to characterise the resonance in 3D is the semi-classical technique of

resonant periodic orbits (RPO)¹³. In this method, the RPOs which satisfy the integral action quantisation condition are determined by a classical trajectory analysis. From these RPOs the resonance energies can be determined. So far this method has been applied only to the lowest energy resonances in the $H+H_2$ and $F+H_2$ reactions. The utility of this method in predicting 3D resonances for the reaction (1) is under study.

Acknowledgement

Calculations reported herein were carried out on the DEC-1090 computer at the Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur. This study was supported in part by a grant from the Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi.

References

1. W. A. CHUPKA and M. E. RUSSELL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **49**, 5426; W. A. CHUPKA, J. BERKOWITZ and R. E. RUSSELL, Sixth International Conference on the Physics of Electronic and Atomic Collisions, M. I. T. Press, Cambridge, 1969, p. 71; W. A. CHUPKA, in "Ion-Molecule Reactions", ed. J. O. FRANKLIN, Plenum, New York, 1972, Vol. 1, p. 72.
2. D. R. McLAUGHLIN and D. L. THOMPSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1979, **70**, 2748.
3. T. JOSEPH and N. SATHYAMURTHY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1984, **80**, 5332; T. JOSEPH, Ph.D. Thesis, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, 1983, and references therein.
4. A. KUPFERMANN and G. C. SCHATZ, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, **62**, 2502; G. C. SCHATZ and A. KUPFERMANN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1976, **65**, 4668.
5. A. B. ELKOWITZ and R. E. WYATT, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, **62**, 2504; 1975, **63**, 702.
6. D. J. KOURI and M. BARR, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1974, **24**, 37; J. T. ADAMS, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1975, **33**, 275; F. M. CHAPMAN, JR. and E. F. HAYES, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, **62**, 4400.
7. P. J. KUNTZ, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1972, **16**, 581.
8. P. J. BROWN and E. F. HAYES, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1971, **55**, 922.
9. J. C. LIGHT and R. B. WALKER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1976, **65**, 1598, 4272; R. B. WALKER, J. C. LIGHT, A. ALTENBERGER-SICZEK, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1976, **64**, 1166; E. B. STECHL, R. B. WALKER and J. C. LIGHT, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1978, **69**, 3518; R. B. WALKER, RXN1D, Program No. 352, Quantum Chemistry Program Exchange, Indiana University, Bloomington.
10. P. J. KUNTZ and W. N. WHITTON, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1975, **34**, 340; W. N. WHITTON and P. J. KUNTZ, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1976, **64**, 3624.
11. R. E. WYATT, J. F. McNUTT and M. J. REDMON, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **86**, 497.
12. C. L. SHORMAKER and R. E. WYATT, *Adv. Quantum Chem.*, 1981, **14**, 171; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1982, **77**, 4982, 4994.
13. E. POLLAK and M. S. CHILD, *Chem. Phys.*, 1981, **60**, 23; E. POLLAK, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1982, **76**, 5843; E. POLLAK and R. E. WYATT, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1982, **77**, 2689.